

YOLO-Based Safety Detection System for Real-Time Hazard Recognition

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Abstract— Machine learning techniques, notably the YOLO (You Only Look Once) object identification model, power the safety identification system. The system aims to automatically identify critical safety equipment in user-uploaded photos or videos. The system effectively recognizes safety gear, including helmets, safety vests, gloves, and glasses, thanks to the integration of YOLO. The technology helps ensure workplace safety compliance by giving real-time feedback on the existence or lack of safety measures. This paper covers the architecture and operation of the Safety Detection System, highlighting its useful applications in various industrial contexts. Additionally, it looks at possible improvements and future research areas to further increase workplace safety monitoring and accident prevention.

Keyword—Machine Learning, Object Detection, YOLO, Image Processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, workplace safety is a top responsibility, necessitating strong measures to guarantee workers' wellbeing. Using state-of-the-art technology together provides a viable way to strengthen safety procedures and reduce hazards. Machine learning stands out among these technologies as a powerful tool for automating safety monitoring and proactive risk management.

This webinar presents a cutting-edge machine learning-powered safety detection system that makes use of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) object identification paradigm. By automatically recognizing vital safety equipment in user-uploaded photos or videos, this system marks a significant advancement in workplace safety. The system skillfully recognizes important safety gear, including helmets, safety vests, gloves, and glasses, in real-time by utilizing YOLO's capabilities.

This system's primary strength is its quick assessment of safety precautions, which gives organizations the capacity to guarantee compliance and promote a safety culture. In order to shed light on its practical uses in a variety of industrial environments, the study explores the architectural subtleties of the system.

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It also looks at directions for future study and development, imagining improvements to support efforts to reduce accidents and improve safety monitoring. This session aims to enhance the conversation on utilizing technology to create safer work environments and more efficient risk mitigation techniques by exploring the intersection of machine learning and workplace safety.

II. RELATED WORKS

- A. In et al. [1], a deep learning model is discussed, designed to detect Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) at construction sites, with the aim of reducing risks. The paper emphasizes the critical role of PPE in preventing accidents and outlines how the model identifies instances of PPE negligence and unauthorized access, aiding security personnel. Additionally, it utilizes facial recognition technology to alert officers of individuals without proper PPE. Experimental results validate the model's effectiveness, showing a Mean Average Precision score of 0.95.
- B. The authors of the paper [2] propose an innovative approach to ensure the proper use of personal protective equipment (PPE) on construction sites. To automatically identify workers who do not employ personal protective equipment (PPE), they integrate geometry connection analysis with deep learning-based object detection. The testing results demonstrate the ability to identify NPU workers with high accuracy (84.13%) and recall rate (93.10%), all while maintaining real-time performance (7.95 FPS on average).
- C. The authors of the paper [3] provide YOLO, a cutting-edge method for object identification. YOLO reframes object detection as a regression problem, directly predicting bounding boxes and class probabilities from complete photos in a single evaluation. This unified architecture enables real-time processing, with the base YOLO model

processing 45 frames per second and the Fast YOLO processing an astounding 155 frames per second. Despite possible localization issues, YOLO outperforms conventional detection techniques like DPM and R-CNN, demonstrating improved generalization across several domains and fewer false positives on background. This document offers insightful information on how to use image and video uploads for real-time safety inspections.

- D. In the article [4] an improved-YOLOv3 method for safety intelligent detection and identification. This method addresses the challenge of non-contact online monitoring of workers wearing safety helmets and protective clothing. The improved-YOLOv3 algorithm incorporates a large-size input layer for multi-scale prediction and adjusts the size of anchor boxes to enhance the detection ability of small-size helmets and protective clothing. It meets real-time supervision requirements with sufficient frames per second (FPS) and achieves higher mean Average Precision (mAP).
- E. The authors of [5] describe a brand-new deep learning technique for quickly and precisely identifying the use of safety helmets on building sites. With YOLO v5 serving as the basis, they add improvements like adding a fourth detection scale and putting in place an attention mechanism in the network's backbone to produce more illuminating features. They employ transfer learning techniques and targeted data augmentation to address the data scarcity. The resultant model runs at a fast speed of only 3.0 ms per image at a resolution of 640×640 and achieves a mean average precision of 92.2%, indicating a 6.3% improvement over the previous approach.
- F. In the article [6] the authors propose a novel approach to enhance safety in construction sites. Combining Transfer Learning-based Instance Segmentation and Data Augmentation with YOLOv8, the model achieves a high mean Average Precision (mAP) of 94.4%. YOLOv8's real-time object recognition capabilities facilitate precise identification of safety-critical objects in diverse construction environments. Transfer learning enhances the model's ability to identify safety-critical elements by leveraging pre-existing knowledge. Advanced data augmentation techniques ensure the model's resilience and adaptability to various environmental conditions at construction sites. This study aims to advance computer vision technologies for real-time safety monitoring and compliance enforcement, paving the way for improved safety protocols in dynamic construction environments.
- G. A framework for worker re-identification

(ReID) and personal protective equipment (PPE) classification-based vision-based site safety compliance monitoring is published in [7]. Deep learning-based technologies are used to address the challenges of monitoring worker behavior on construction sites. The study proposes a weighted-class technique for PPE classification and introduces a novel loss function for ReID called similarity loss in order to lessen model bias. The study combines data from ReID and PPE classification to create a way to track instances of workers not donning the necessary personal protective equipment (PPE).

- H. The authors of [8] suggest an AI-based method for keeping an eye on safety helmet usage on building sites. The solution uses computer vision to identify whether or not employees are using safety helmets on Android cellphones. Workers receive real-time notifications through audio alarms on their smartphones, and the safety manager receives them via SMS. A Firebase database contains records of the actions of the workers. The program intends to add more features in the future, such as worker record-based incentives and penalties.

III. METHODOLOGY

The Safety Detection System leverages machine learning algorithms, notably the YOLO (You Only Look Once) object detection model, to automatically recognize crucial safety gear in images or videos provided by users. By integrating YOLO, the system adeptly identifies safety essentials like helmets, safety vests, gloves, and glasses, offering instant feedback on safety compliance. This paper delves into the system's architecture, its operational framework, and its practical utility across diverse industrial environments. The methodology includes:

A. Image Processing:

The preprocessing stage initiates by opening the image file uploaded by the user. This image is then converted into a NumPy array for subsequent processing. To align with the requirements of OpenCV, which operates in the BGR color space, the color space of the image is transformed from RGB to BGR. This conversion ensures compatibility with further image processing operations, particularly when employing OpenCV's functionalities for object detection or other computer vision tasks.

```
def detect(file):  
    model = YOLO('yolov8s_custom.pt')  
    if file.type == "image/png" or file.type == "image/jpeg":  
        image = Image.open(file)  
        frame = cv2.cvtColor(np.array(image), cv2.COLOR_RGB2BGR)
```

B. Safety Detection:

The YOLO (You Only Look Once) object detection model, integrated via the Ultralytics library, is harnessed for identifying safety gear within the image. This model arrives pre-trained, equipped to discern various objects, encompassing vital safety equipment like helmets, gloves, glasses, and safety vests.

- Helmet
- Helmet
- Helmet
- Safety-Vest
- Safety-Vest
- Gloves

```
def detect(file):
    model = YOLO('yolov8s_custom.pt')
    classes = []
    safety = ['Glass', 'Gloves', 'Helmet', 'Safety-Vest', 'helmet']
    safety_detected = []
    if safety_detected:
        st.image(frame, channels="BGR")
        st.write("Safety measures present in the image:")
        for measure in safety_detected:
            st.write(f"- {measure}")
```

C. Drawing Boxes and Labels Exploratory :

Detected safety equipment is outlined with bounding boxes and labeled with their respective classes. This is done using OpenCV functions to draw rectangles and text on the image.

```
for r in results:
    for c in r.boxes:
        if model.names[int(c.cls)] in safety:
            class_name = model.names[int(c.cls)]
            classes.append(model.names[int(c.cls)])
            x1, y1, x2, y2 = map(int, c.xyxy[0])
            cv2.rectangle(frame, (x1, y1), (x2, y2), (255, 0, 255), 2)
            cv2.putText(frame, class_name, (x1, y1 - 10), cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 0.5, (255, 0, 255), 2)
            safety_detected.append(c.class_name)
```

D. Result

Safety Detection System

c1.jpeg 11.0KB

Safety measures present in the image:

Figure1.Output Result

IV. CONCLUSION

The YOLO object detection model enables the Safety Detection System, a noteworthy advancement in workplace safety. By automatically recognizing essential safety equipment like helmets, vests, gloves, and glasses in user-supplied photos or videos, the system provides real-time safety compliance information. Its seamless incorporation into industrial environments fosters a proactive attitude toward accident avoidance, as well as strengthening adherence to safety regulations. This extensive document carefully outlines the architecture and functional structure of the system, highlighting its real benefits in a variety of sectors. Furthermore, it delves into future directions for investigation and possible improvements, encapsulating a continuous effort to improve safety surveillance procedures and reduce occupational injuries.

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